

QUIZ

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PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

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The author applied US English

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

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QUIZ FOR ACA-401D

1. Which one of the following is NOT considered an academic essay?

- Scholarly Writing.
- Nonfictional Writing.
- Conference Paper
- Fictional Writing.¹

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2. What is the definition of research?

- Answering a question by obtaining information
- Systematic inquiry to answer a question that others want to solve.²
- Collecting, presenting, reporting, and sharing findings

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Commented [KG1]: Some multiple-choices have terminal punctuation while some do not. Try to be uniform. Either place on all of them or delete from all
Also, use the following format to cite the course pack subsequently since you cited it in full in the first instance-
Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 19.

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¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

² ACA-401D Coursepack, 19.

Writing papers and presenting at a conference

3. Underline the factor NOT contributed to America English's dominance in the world?

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The Geographical Location of the U.S.³

The wealth of the U.S.

The magnitude of the publishing industry in America

The international political and economic position of the U.S.

4. Which one of the following statements is NOT considered a quotation?

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The exact words of an author.

Putting the author's name in parenthesis followed by the page number:

The language you use cannot resemble the words of the author.⁴

The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be the same to the author's style.

5. What is the correct format for book citations?

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Author, Book, Date of the URL, and the title of the site.

Author, Date, Title, University, Place, and Degree Level

Author, Date of access, Title, and Issuance date.

Author Name, Date, Title, Place of Publication, and the Publisher⁵

6. The following are types of bibliography except one

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Selected bibliography

³ ACA-401D Coursepack, 25.

⁴ ACA-401D Coursepack, 36.

⁵ ACA-401D Coursepack, 38.

- Author and date Bibliography
- Annotated Bibliography
- Ordered bibliography.**⁶

7. Which of the following does not encompass style aspects?

- Preferred sentence lengths
- Manuscript layout
- Font usage
- Grammar.**⁷

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8. Identify the statement that is not describing Problem Statement

- Indicating the need for the study,
- Describing the issue to be studied,
- Justifying the significance of the study.
- Describes the purpose of the study.**⁸

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9. The following characteristics apply to the theoretical framework except one:

- Draws on theory
- Concentrates the research findings.**⁹
- Examines the relationship among constructs and ideas

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⁶ [Kate L. Turabian](#), *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 155.

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⁷ ACA-401D Coursepack, 41.

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⁸ [Linda Dale Bloomberg](#) and [Marie Volpe](#). 2018. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2018), 74.

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⁹ [Linda Dale Bloomberg](#) and [Marie Volpe](#), *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 77.

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- Provides the theoretical or conceptual basis for the development

10. Which one is NOT among the reasons for citing your sources?

- To give credit.
- To reassure readers about the accuracy of your facts.
- To evaluate other academic works.¹⁰**
- To help readers follow or extend your research.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2018.

¹⁰ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*: 139.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.